

Effects of intervention protocol regarding permanent pacemaker implantation on nurse's knowledge, practices and patients' outcomes

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ABSTRACT: Background: Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) are a major global health issue, causing illness and death across the world. Cardiac arrhythmias, irregular heart rhythms, are a particularly serious aspect of CVDs. Pacemakers are used to manage arrhythmias by sending electrical signals to the heart. Therefore aim of the study is to assess the effect of intervention protocols for permanent pacemaker implantation on nurses' knowledge and practices, as well as their influence on patient outcomes.

Methodology: A quasi-experimental study design was conducted among 114 nurses during the months from June 2023 to November 2023 at Faisalabad Institute of Cardiology. Purposive sampling was used for patients who met specific criteria. Various tools, including questionnaires and checklists, were employed to collect data from both nurses and patients, covering demographics, knowledge, and nursing practices.

Results: The results of study revealed that majority (50.9%) of the participants had age group 26-30 year and a predominantly female gender (91.2%). Most respondents were unmarried, and had varying education levels and work experience. A notable percentage had not received training in cardiac surgery and pacemaker procedures. The findings of study revealed significant improvements in knowledge, nursing practices and patients' outcomes following an intervention.

Conclusion: The study concluded that an intervention protocol significantly improved nurses' knowledge and practices regarding permanent pacemaker implantation, resulting in better patients' outcomes. The findings emphasized the importance of ongoing education and guidelines in enhancing the quality of care in this context, benefitting both healthcare professionals and patients.

Keywords: Intervention Protocol, Nurses' Knowledge, Nurses' Practices, Patients' Outcomes, Cardiac Care, Nursing Education, Permanent Pacemaker Implantation

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1. Introduction

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) remain a global health challenge, contributing significantly to morbidity and mortality rates worldwide (1). Among various manifestations of CVDs, cardiac arrhythmias stand out as a critical concern. These arrhythmias can range

from benign to life-threatening, significantly impacting an individual's quality of life and, in severe cases, leading to cardiac arrest (2). The proper management of arrhythmias is essential to mitigate their adverse effects on patients.

Cardiac arrhythmias can result from various causes, including structural heart disease, electrolyte imbalances, and age-related changes in the heart's conduction system (3). Some arrhythmias are transient and self-limiting, while others are persistent and require medical intervention (4). In cases where the heart's electrical system fails to function properly, the use of pacemakers becomes a crucial therapeutic option (5).

The management of arrhythmias often necessitates the use of pacemakers. Pacemakers play a pivotal role in restoring and maintaining appropriate heart rhythms, thereby enhancing the patient's overall well-being (6). Permanent pacemakers enhance the well-being of numerous patients and, for the majority, prove to be potentially life-saving devices (7).

Cardiac electrophysiologists routinely perform the task of regularly monitoring implanted permanent pacemakers (8). Additionally, these patients often experience the need for emergency hospitalization and prolonged stays, leading to a diminished quality of life (9). Therefore, nurses assume a crucial role in the care of patients with permanent pacemakers by staying abreast of pacemaker technology through continuous training and education (10). Nurses are recognized for their significant role in collaborating with the multidisciplinary team and providing information to patients and their families before surgery (11). Enhanced nurse knowledge and practices contribute to safer procedures and improved post-implantation care, thereby lowering the risk of complications for patients with permanent pacemakers.

Main objective of the study is to measure the knowledge and practices of nurses, caring patients with permanent Pacemaker implantation and to evaluate the effect of educating nurses regarding care guidelines about permanent pacemaker before and after implantation.

2. Material & Methods

A quasi-experimental study with a single-group pre-post approach was conducted at Faisalabad Institute of Cardiology (FIC), Faisalabad. A sample size of 114 cases was determined with a 95% confidence interval, a 5% margin of error, and an anticipated percentage of knowledge (pre-post difference) regarding permanent pacemaker patient care among staff nurses estimated at 20%. Data were gathered from nurses and patients using a convenient sampling technique. Male and females nurses working in "Cath Lab" Faisalabad Institute of Cardiology Faisalabad with at least 6 month of working experience were included in study. Nurses working in other department were excluded. Male and females patients admitted for permanent pacemaker implantation were included and psychiatric patients having any other co-morbidity were excluded from the study. In the study, the researcher used three tools: a knowledge questionnaire, a practice observation checklist, and a patient output questionnaire (12). Knowledge questionnaire for nurses consists of 10 multiple choice questions. Nurses' practice checklist consists of 10 items regarding permanent pacemaker patient's care. The patients' output was checked using Barthel Index Scale. After getting ethical approval from Research Ethical Committee of University of Lahore and written permission from study setting, data were collected from nurses and patients of Critical care units and cardiac wards. Data was collected at two points, pre and post educational intervention. Pre-data was collected from participants before intervention phase. The researcher administered the nursing intervention protocol through a series of nine sessions, conducted over the span of one week, with three sessions per week. Each session lasted between 30 to 45 minutes. Intervention completed

in five months from May 2023 to September 2023. After educational intervention, researcher collected post data from nurses and patients from September 2023 to October 2023. The analysis of data was performed utilizing SPSS version 25.0. The Wilcoxon signed-rank test was employed as the statistical method to test the hypothesis.

3. Results

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Nurses

Demographic characteristics	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Age		
20-25 years	18	15.8
26-30years	40	50.9s
31-35years	44	38.6
36-40years	12	10.5
Mean ±SD	2.44±0.88	
Min-Max	1-4	
1. Gender		
Male	10	8.8
Female	104	91.2
3. Marital Status		
Unmarried	72	63.2
Married	29	25.4
Widow / Divorced	13	11.4
4. Professional Education		
General Nursing and Midwifery	38	33.3
Post RN BSN	37	32.5
BSN	37	32.5
MSN	2	1.8
5. Work Experience		
6 Months	13	11.4
1 Year	40	35.1
2 Years	25	21.9
More than 2 Year	36	31.6
6. Training for cardiac surgery		
No	62	54.4
Yes	52	45.6
7. Work Experience in cardiology /ICU		
6 Months	34	29.8
1 Year	25	21.9
2 Years	29	25.4
More than 2 Year	26	22.8
8. Training for pacemaker		
Not trained	83	72.8
Trained	31	27.2

Table 1 shows that majority aged 26-30 years (50.9%). Females constitute 91.2%, and 63.2% are unmarried. Educational backgrounds are evenly distributed, with Diploma in General Nursing and Midwifery being the most common (33.3%). Respondents with 1 year of work experience (35.1%) dominate, while 54.4% have not received training in cardiac

surgery. Experience in cardiology/ICU ranges from 6 months (29.8%) to over 2 years (22.8%). For pacemaker procedures, 72.8% lack training.

Table 2: Mean knowledge score difference among pre and post interventional groups

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Pre-Interventional Knowledge	114	3.6053	4.25434	.00	10.00
Post-Interventional Knowledge	114	8.2018	1.06580	6.00	10.00
Ranks					
		N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	
Pre-Interventional Knowledge Post-Interventional Knowledge	Negative Ranks	32 ^a	18.98	607.50	
	Positive Ranks	77 ^b	69.97	5387.50	
	Ties	5 ^c			
	Total	114			
Test Statistics					
Z					-7.249 ^b
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)					.000
a. Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test					
b. Based on negative ranks.					

Table 2 shows a significant improvement in participants' knowledge after an educational intervention. The initial average score was 3.6053, but post-intervention, it rose to 8.2018. Statistical analysis (Z-statistic: -7.249, p-value: .000) confirms the intervention's significance.

Table 3: Mean Practices score difference among pre and post interventional group

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Pre-Interventional Practices	114	7.1316	3.36434	2.00	13.00
Post-Interventional Practices	114	13.4825	4.60902	4.00	19.00
Ranks					
		N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	
Pre-Interventional Practices Post-Interventional Practices	Negative Ranks	15 ^d	31.73	476.00	
	Positive Ranks	99 ^e	61.40	6079.00	
	Ties	0 ^f			
	Total	114			
Test Statistics					
Z					-7.940 ^b
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)					.000
a. Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test					
b. Based on negative ranks.					

Table 3 analyses the mean practices score difference before and after intervention. Initially, the mean score was 7.1316, increasing post-intervention to 13.4825. Negative ranks (mean rank: 31.73) likely represent those with lower initial scores, while positive ranks (mean rank: 61.40) indicate significant improvements. A Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test (Z-statistic: -7.940, p-value: .000) confirms a highly significant difference in practices scores.

This section shows the demographic characteristics of patients who participated in study.

Table 4: Demographic Characteristics of Studied Patients

Demographic characteristics	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Age		
40-50 years	21	18.4
51-60 years	57	50
61-70 years	36	31.6
Mean $\pm$SD	2.131 $\pm$ 0.697	
Gender		
Male	89	78.1
Female	25	21.9
3. Marital Status		
Unmarried	40	35.1
Married	74	64.9
4. Education		
Matriculation	42	36.8
Intermediate	49	43
Bachelor or above	23	20.2
5. Residence		
Rural	38	33.3
Urban	76	66.7
6. Occupation		
Officer	45	39.5
Laborer/ Farmer	22	19.3
Usual house work	47	41.2
7. Income		
Not Enough	35	30.7
Enough	79	69.3
8. Smoking		
Yes	78	68.4
No	36	31.6

Table 4 summarizes demographic characteristics of studied patients. Most were aged 51-60 years (50%) and predominantly male (78.1%). The majority were married (64.9%), with intermediate education (43%). Urban residents constituted 66.7%, and common occupations included usual housework (41.2%) and Officers (39.5%). Most patients considered their income sufficient (69.3%), and the majority were non-smokers (68.4%).

Table 5: Medical History of Studied Patients

Demographic characteristics	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Clinical presentation at admission		
Tachycardia	24	21.1
Bradycardia	21	18.4
Dizziness	20	17.5
Chest pain	49	43.0
Previous chronic disease		
Yes	65	57.0
No	49	43.0
Comorbid disease		
Other cardiac disease	10	32.5
Hypertension	37	46.5
Diabetes	53	12.3
Renal disease	14	
Family history of Pacemaker Implantation		
Yes	72	63.2
No	42	36.8
Family cardiac disease		
Coronary heart disease	25	21.9
Cardiac stroke	21	18.4
Heart failure	40	35.1
Hypertension	28	24.6

Table 5 outlines the medical history of studied patients. Common symptoms at admission included chest pain (43.0%) and tachycardia (21.1%). A majority had a history of chronic diseases (57.0%), with hypertension being the most prevalent (46.5%). Family history indicated 63.2% had a family history of medical conditions. Family cardiac diseases included heart failure (35.1%) and coronary heart disease (21.9%).

Table 6: Mean Difference between Patient Outcomes before and After Intervention

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Pre-Patient Outcomes	114	13.4825	4.60902	4.00	19.00
Post- Patient Outcomes	114	19.1053	1.71081	15.00	22.00
Ranks					
		N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	
Pre Patient Outcomes	Negative Ranks	0 ^g	.00	.00	
Post Patient Outcomes	Positive Ranks	114 ^h	57.50	6555.00	
	Ties	0 ⁱ			
	Total	114			
Test Statistics					
Z			-9.284 ^b		
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)			.000		
a. Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test					
b. Based on negative ranks.					

Table 6 shows the mean difference in patient outcomes before and after intervention. Initially, the mean score was 13.4825, increasing post-intervention to 19.1053.

Positive ranks (mean rank: 57.50) indicate improvement for all patients. A Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test (Z-statistic: -9.284, p-value: .000) confirms a highly significant difference, rejecting the null hypothesis. The study underscores the effectiveness of educating nurses on pacemaker care guidelines in improving patient outcomes.

4. Discussion

Nurses play a critical role in the care of patients who have pacemakers. To excel in this role, they need to have a deep understanding of the specific needs and priorities associated with pacemaker patients (13).

The current research indicates that a significant portion of the nurses examined before intervention possessed Unsatisfactory Knowledge about pacemaker devices. This result is consistent with a prior investigation conducted by Mohammed et al. (2016)(14), which also found that approximately 80% of the nurses examined had insufficient knowledge about pacemakers. This was also in agreement with a study Thabet et al.(2019) (15) who identified that 77.5% of nurses possessed an insufficient level of knowledge concerning the care of patients with temporary pacemakers. Another study conducted by Muizz Ismail et al(2020) (10) reported that 32.9 % nurses had a limited knowledge in managing patients with pacemaker implantation. (16). In line with these findings, Snegalatha et al (2019) (17) also supported these findings.

The current study revealed that the majority of the nurses examined had unsatisfactory practice levels when it came to caring for patients with permanent pacemakers. This finding aligns with a study conducted by Bayomi (2020) (12), which also observed that most of the nurses in their study had unsatisfactory practice levels in caring for patients with permanent pacemakers. The current study has indicated a decrease in nurses' performance in caring for patients with implantable pacemakers before the introduction of the intervention protocol. This findings was in agreement with Thabet et al.(2019) (15) According to their findings, the study reported that 92.5% of nurses exhibited unsatisfactory practices in caring for patients with temporary pacemakers. Hassan etal (2022) (18) also supported these findings.

In evaluating the daily living activities of patients with implantable pacemakers, the study's results reveal a significant improvement across all scale items concerning patient outcomes. These results align with the findings of Elgazzar (2021) (16) who also noted an increased level of independence in the execution of daily living activities, encompassing feeding, bathing, grooming, mobility, transfer, toilet use, and stair use, among individuals in the experimental group. These findings are further substantiated by another study conducted by Ali et al.(2021) (19), who reported improvement in the daily living activities of patients after implementation of education intervention. Khalil et al. (2020) (20) also supported these findings as study reported that patient outcomes improved after intervention.

5. Conclusion

The study revealed several key findings related to nurses' knowledge, practices, and patient outcomes regarding permanent pacemaker implantation. Following the implementation of an intervention protocol, nurses showed a significant improvement in both their knowledge and practices. The intervention had a positive impact on enhancing nurses' understanding and ability to provide care for patients with pacemakers, contributing to better patient outcomes. Additionally, the study provided valuable insights into the demographic characteristics of the participants, shedding light on the diverse backgrounds of both nurses and patients involved. The study's results have practical implications for

healthcare professionals, emphasizing the significance of ongoing training and support to enhance patient outcomes and overall quality of care.

List of Abbreviations

CVDs: Cardiovascular diseases

FIC: Faisalabad Institute of Cardiology

Ethics Approval and Consent to Participate

Ethically permission to conduct the study was taken from Research Ethics Committee of Faculty of Allied Health Sciences, The University of Lahore via the reference number REC-UOL-417-05-2023.

Conflict of interest

None

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